

LINGUAL ANALYSIS USAGE OF BODY PARTS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH IDIOMS

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ABSTRACT

Phrases are a special form of language that can take the form of word units and sentences. In recent years, the use of body parts in idioms has involved a lot of research. This article discusses the use of body parts in English and Uzbek language phrases. At the same time, it promotes the development of these languages and the development of communication in them.

Key words: Body parts, similarities, differences, English, Uzbek, phrases.

ANNOTATSIYA

Iboralar – bu so‘z birliklari va gaplar shaklini olishi mumkin bo‘lgan tilning maxsus shakli. So‘nggi yillarda tana a‘zolaridan iboralarda foydalanish ko‘plab izlanishlarni talab qilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada tana a‘zolaridan ingliz va o‘zbek tilidagi iboralarda foydalanish haqida so‘z boradi. Shu bilan birga, bu ushbu tillarning rivojlanishiga va ulardagi aloqaning rivojlanishiga yordam beradi.

Tayanch so‘zlar: Tana qismlari, o‘xshashliklari, farqlari, inglizcha, o‘zbekcha, iboralar.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Фразы – это особая форма языка, которая может принимать форму словарных единиц и предложений. В последние годы использование частей тела в идиомах стало предметом множества исследований. В этой статье обсуждается использование частей тела в фразах на английском и узбекском языках. В то же время он способствует развитию этих языков и развитию общения на них.

Ключевые слова: Части тела, сходство, различия, английский, узбекский, фразы.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbek and English are languages with a long history, and idioms in both languages have accumulated in the long time. Body parts are among the most frequently used words in idioms, and they play an important role in expressions in both languages. This article is based on cognitive linguistics and examines the similarities and differences between the idioms expressed with body parts in English and Uzbek. An in-depth study of the differences between them leads to an in-depth study of both cultures.

Idioms are common in all languages and reflect the culture, history, as well as the beauty of the language. Their structure is different, some of them carry a rich meaning, even though they consist of a few words, while others express different meanings and make the speaker and listener a little hasty. Idioms that include body parts are also widely used in everyday life. Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary defines phrases as the language or grammar used by a particular person in a particular situation. The three most important features of English expressions are: a whole linguistic unit, a structurally cohesive, irreplaceability.

METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

The object of research involves the English and Uzbek idioms. The purpose of the work is to carry out comparative and contrastive analysis of body part idioms in different languages. Materials of this research are idiom books of English and Uzbek, history of both nations. It needs to be emphasized that this article concentrates on comparative study of characteristics of idioms and some features of their translation. The aim of the article is to give general information about the topic which could be helpful in learning and being aware of sophisticated features of these languages through the comparison.

The rigid structure of idioms in two languages.

Some phrases are rigid in structure, and substituting them creates confusion in speech. For example, we can't change the word "black and blue" to "blue and black." Any change in a phrase will result in a major change in its meaning and will not be considered an idiom. Or in Uzbek we can't replace the idiom "Oq qorani tanigan" to "Qora oqni tanigan".

The basis of the exchange of cultures is the human factor. In English and Uzbek, phrases, idioms and proverbs involving body parts are widely used to liken or compare something. Although English and Uzbek are from a completely different language family, there are many similarities in the idioms and sentences in which body parts are involved. Close ties between countries also have an impact on intercultural

communication, and changes in language can lead to enrichment. Idioms can be used in different aspects of life. In this article, we will look at human body idioms that express emotion, advice, and action.

Emotions are common to all human beings and are manifested in various forms, such as anger, fear, joy, and so on. In many cases, idioms involving body parts can be used to express this feeling more strongly and effectively. If to consider English idioms.

1. "Come to a head" – "Pichoq suyakga taqaldi" – to come to the last resort

2. A sight for sore eyes – "Ko'rib ko'zi quvnadi" – To be happy to see something long-awaited

3. That's music to my ears – "Qulog'imga moyday yoqdi" – It is pleasant to listen to it.

These sentences exemplify that in both languages, body parts are used to express emotions. However, in the first sample, the meaning of the idiom is the same, although the word "suyak" is used in Uzbek instead of the word "head" in English. In the second example, the word "Sight" comes to mean "Quvnadi" and creates a certain degree of contextual synonymy. In the third example, the word "Music" in the Uzbek language means "Moy", which means "gentle, pleasant". It is said that the more beautiful the music, the more pleasant it is to listen.

As in all proverbs, there are idioms that give advice that involve body parts.

1. The walls have ears we - Devorning ham qulog'i bor- - don't talk everywhere, manage your speech.

2. Stick the nose in something - Burnini suqmoq - to intrude into something that is not your affair.

Both idioms use the same lexically identical words and have no difficulty in translation. Research shows that phrases can guide people, give advice them no matter what language they are using. As in the examples above, the word structure is the same in terms of meaning, although the two nations are different.

Idioms involving body parts are used not only to express feelings or advice but also actions.

1. All eyes are on- Ikki ko'zi to'rt bo'ldi- wait with anticipation

2. Keep an eye on- Ko'zini uzmay qarash- to be observed

3. See something out of the corner of your eye- Ko'z qirini tashlamoq- To look out of the corner of your eye.

4. Turn a blind eye - Ko'zi ko'r, qulog'i kar - to forget what you have seen and heard and not to tell anyone.

5. Lend an ear- Qulog'im sizda- I can listen to you.

6. Have nose in the air- Burni osmonda bo'lmoq - Looking down at others.

The eyes and ears are used to express movement in the above phrases in English and Uzbek, although they do not have basic locomotor organs. In the first phrase, the English word "all" is synonymous with the Uzbek word "to'rt". In the fourth example, only the word "eye" is used in English, and the word "quloq" also is used in Uzbek. In the fifth example, the verb "lend" is used to mean hearing. In the sixth example, the word "air" is used as an equivalent to the word "osmon."

Causes of similarities and differences

A comparative study of the above examples in English and Uzbek reveals that there are similarities and differences between the idioms in which the body parts of both languages are involved. Analyzing the similarities, we can conclude that in both languages it is based on the common human bodily experience, that is, the similarity of both physical and mental aspects. People feel the same emotions, regardless of nationality. In addition, the similarity in the cognitive base leads to similarities different nations and languages. The intercultural communication that has emerged as a result of globalization is also having an impact on language and cognitive basis of nations. The reasons for the difference in usage of words in idioms related to the historical events, culture, religion, literature, and customs of each nation.

Historical background factor

Ancient civilization of Uzbek dates to more than three thousands years of history. All historical events and historical background clearly reflected Uzbek idioms. During the Karakhanid period (11th-12th centuries), the final stage of the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people began with the transfer of political power to the Turkic dynasties in Movarounnahr and Khorezm. Within the Western Karakhanid state, the modern Uzbek Turkic ethnos was established. During the Karakhanid period (11th-12th centuries), the final stage of the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people began with the transfer of political power to the Turkic dynasties in Movarounnahr and Khorezm. Within the Western Karakhanid state, the modern Uzbek Turkic ethnos was established.

English idioms are closely related to one thousand year history of England which is not so long history incomparasion to Uzbek history. The Roman conquest, the invasion of Scandinavia, the conquest of Normandy and other important events influenced the formation of english idioms. Researching idiom formation of both languages one can learn that history and nations formation emerge language formation. Cultures and languages differ because history is various.

CONCLUSION

In-depth study of phrases leads to the conclusion that idioms are structurally and semantically invariant units that contain different cultural features and information.

This article compares body part idioms in English and Uzbek. As a result of the research, it became clear that the English and Uzbek expressions in which the body parts are present have the same generality and individuality. This research will help people use and understand idioms appropriately in both languages.

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